

GLOBAL OPTIMAL DESIGN OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY AN ADAPTIVE PSO ALGORITHM

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SUMMARY

An adaptive PSO algorithm for the optimal design of composite laminates is presented. The formalization of the optimum problem is completely general and any type of design problem can be considered.

Keywords: laminates, elastic properties, optimization, PSO, polar method.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Particle Swarm Optimization method (PSO) is a metaheuristic introduced by Eberhart and Kennedy [1] to solve complex optimization problems. It mimics in an algebraic way the dynamics of groups of individuals (particles), such as the flocks of birds. Working on a population of individuals (the swarm) rather than on a single particle, the PSO paradigm is in principle well suited to solve hard non-linear non-convex optimization problems. Its main advantage is its true simplicity: a PSO is a zeroth order algorithm, and the standard algorithm is very simple, short and quick. Nevertheless, it depends upon a certain number of parameters, proper to the algorithm itself, which must be chosen to guarantee the convergence, rapidity and robustness of the algorithm itself: this is the so-called problem of *PSO parameters tuning*.

This paper proposes a new PSO algorithm, called ALE-PSO (Adaptive Local Evolution –PSO) and conceived to handle some hard constrained optimal design problems of laminates. The author and co-workers proposed in the past a general way to formulate the optimization of laminates, [2], based upon the polar method, [3], and an enhanced genetic algorithm to handle this kind of problems [4]. The purpose of this paper is to show that PSO algorithms can be effectively used for this type of problems, but that, for the hardest of them, an adaptive strategy of parameters tuning must be adopted. In fact, the main feature of ALE-PSO is the possibility to let evolve these parameters along iterations, following a scheduled power law specified by the user and chosen according to some criteria of convergence and stability.

2. POLAR FORMULATION OF DESIGN PROBLEMS FOR LAMINATES

The design of laminates must take into account, besides the objective itself, also the general elastic properties of the final laminate. The general constitutive law of an elastic laminate is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^o \\ \boldsymbol{\chi} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{M} are the tensors of in-plane tractions and of bending moments, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0$ is the tensor of in-plane strains for the middle plane, $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ is the tensor of curvatures. The 4th order tensors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{D} describe respectively the in- and out-of-plane behaviour of the plate, while \mathbf{B} take into account coupling between them. Usually, designers look for laminates having an orthotropic behaviour, at least in extension, and uncoupled, *i.e.* $\mathbf{B}=\mathbf{O}$, but other elastic properties can also be of interest. All these properties can be taken into account by the following minimization procedure, [2]: consider the quadratic form $I(\mathbf{P})$ of the symmetric matrix \mathbf{H} :

$$I(\mathbf{P}) = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P} = H_{ij} P_i P_j, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 18 \quad (2)$$

with the components of vector \mathbf{P} given by

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= \frac{\bar{T}_0}{h M}, \quad P_2 = \frac{\bar{T}_1}{h M}, \quad P_3 = \frac{\bar{R}_0}{h M}, \quad P_4 = \frac{\bar{R}_1}{h M}, \quad P_5 = \bar{\Phi}_0, \quad P_6 = \bar{\Phi}_1, \\ P_7 &= \frac{2 \hat{T}_0}{h^2 M}, \quad P_8 = \frac{2 \hat{T}_1}{h^2 M}, \quad P_9 = \frac{2 \hat{R}_0}{h^2 M}, \quad P_{10} = \frac{2 \hat{R}_1}{h^2 M}, \quad P_{11} = \hat{\Phi}_0, \quad P_{12} = \hat{\Phi}_1, \\ P_{13} &= \frac{12 \tilde{T}_0}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{14} = \frac{12 \tilde{T}_1}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{15} = \frac{12 \tilde{R}_0}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{16} = \frac{12 \tilde{R}_1}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{17} = \tilde{\Phi}_0, \quad P_{18} = \tilde{\Phi}_1. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, h is the total laminate thickness while M is a factor, whose dimensions are those of an elastic modulus, used to obtain non-dimensional variables, which can be chosen in various ways. In addition,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_0, \hat{T}_0, \tilde{T}_0 &= \frac{1}{\mu} \sum_{k=1}^{np} T_{0k} (z_k^\mu - z_{k-1}^\mu), \\ \bar{T}_1, \hat{T}_1, \tilde{T}_1 &= \frac{1}{\mu} \sum_{k=1}^{np} T_{1k} (z_k^\mu - z_{k-1}^\mu), \\ \bar{R}_0 e^{4i\bar{\Phi}_0}, \hat{R}_0 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_0}, \tilde{R}_0 e^{4i\tilde{\Phi}_0} &= \frac{1}{\mu} \sum_{k=1}^{np} R_{0k} e^{4i(\Phi_{0k} + \delta_k)} (z_k^\mu - z_{k-1}^\mu), \\ \bar{R}_1 e^{4i\bar{\Phi}_1}, \hat{R}_1 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_1}, \tilde{R}_1 e^{4i\tilde{\Phi}_1} &= \frac{1}{\mu} \sum_{k=1}^{np} R_{1k} e^{4i(\Phi_{1k} + \delta_k)} (z_k^\mu - z_{k-1}^\mu), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

are, in complex form, the 18 polar components of, respectively, tensor \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} , with $\mu=1$ for \mathbf{A} , $\mu=2$ for \mathbf{B} and $\mu=3$ for \mathbf{D} ; np is the number of plies in the stack and δ_k is the orientation angle of the k -th ply; T_{0k} , T_{1k} , R_{0k} , R_{1k} , Φ_{0k} and Φ_{1k} are the polar parameters of the k -th layer. The polar parameters of an elastic plane tensor \mathbf{L} are given, in complex form, by the following functions of the Cartesian components of \mathbf{L} :

$$\begin{aligned} 8T_0 &= L_{1111} - 2L_{1122} + 4L_{1212} + L_{2222}, \\ 8T_1 &= L_{1111} + 2L_{1122} + L_{2222}, \\ 8R_0 e^{4i\Phi_0} &= L_{1111} - 2L_{1122} - 4L_{1212} + L_{2222} + 4i(L_{1112} - L_{2212}), \\ 8R_1 e^{2i\Phi_1} &= L_{1111} - L_{2222} + 2i(L_{1112} + L_{2212}). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The advantage of using polar parameters is their capability to express as simply as possible the symmetries of the elastic behaviour; actually, \mathbf{L} is orthotropic if and only if $\Phi_0 - \Phi_1 = K \frac{\pi}{4}$, $K = 0, 1$; \mathbf{L} is R_0 -orthotropic, [5], if and only if $R_0 = 0$; \mathbf{L} is square-symmetric if and only if $R_1 = 0$; \mathbf{L} is isotropic if and only if $R_0 = R_1 = 0$. For more details on the results of the polar method, the reader is addressed to the original paper of Verchery, [3], or to [6].

\mathbf{H} is a symmetric matrix of real coefficients: putting the components H_{ij} to chosen values \hat{H}_{ij} determines the kind of problem to be treated. Several choices are possible, so several different problems can be stated in the same way, simply changing the \hat{H}_{ij} . \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite and each problem of determining a laminate having some specified general elastic properties can be stated as follows:

$$\min_{\delta_k, k=1, \dots, np} I(\mathbf{P}) = H_{ij} P_i(\delta_k) P_j(\delta_k), \quad \text{with} \quad H_{ij} = \hat{H}_{ij} \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 18. \quad (6)$$

As \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite, these minimums are zero-valued (except in the case of $K=1$ orthotropy). Clearly, to solve such a problem means to find a vector \mathbf{P} satisfying the above statement. As $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{P}(\delta_k)$, cfr. eqns. (3) and (4), the true design variables of the problem are the orientations δ_k . Eqns. (4) are highly non-linear and non convex with respect to the δ_k , so also function $I(\mathbf{P})$ is non-linear and non-convex.

It is worth noting that parameters P_i generalise the concept of lamination parameters introduced by Miki, [7-8], and successively widely used by several authors, but unlike these they have some advantages: they are based upon tensor invariants linked to elastic symmetries, so their use allows a very simple statement of problems concerning these symmetries and in addition they make directly appear the orientation of the reference or material frame.

Of course, the optimal design of laminates cannot be reduced to the unique design of elastic properties; normally, designers want to minimize or maximize a given quantity (volume, stiffness etc.) or to obtain minimum requirements. Then, we will consider here also problems of the type

$$\min_{\delta_k, k=1, \dots, np} I(\mathbf{P}) = H_{ij} P_i(\delta_k) P_j(\delta_k), \quad (7)$$

with $H_{ij} = \hat{H}_{ij} \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 18$, and $g_j[P_i(\delta_k)] \leq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, nc$,

with $g_j[P_i(\delta_k)]$ a generic constraint imposed to the problem and nc the total number of constraints.

3. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CODE ALE-PSO

The general structure of the code ALE-PSO is that of a classical PSO algorithm, which can be condensed in the following updating rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{t+1}^k &= r_0 c_0 \mathbf{u}_t^k + r_1 c_1 (\mathbf{p}_t^k - \mathbf{x}_t^k) + r_2 c_2 (\mathbf{p}_t^g - \mathbf{x}_t^k), \\ \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k &= \mathbf{x}_t^k + \mathbf{u}_{t+1}^k, \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, m, \quad t = 1, \dots, s. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where: \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k is a vector representing the position, in the n -dimensional problem space, of the k -th particle in a swarm of m particles, at the time-step $t+1$ of s total steps; \mathbf{u}_{t+1}^k is the displacement (often called velocity) of the particle \mathbf{x}^k from its position \mathbf{x}_t^k at the time step t to its updated position \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k at the time-step $t+1$; \mathbf{p}_t^k is the vector recording the best position occupied so far by the k -th particle (personal best position); in a minimization problem for the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$, \mathbf{p}_t^k is updated as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_{t+1}^k = \begin{cases} \mathbf{p}_t^k, & \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k) \geq f(\mathbf{p}_t^k), \\ \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k, & \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k) < f(\mathbf{p}_t^k). \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Moreover, \mathbf{p}_t^g is the vector recording the best position occupied so far by any particle in the swarm (global best position); in a minimization problem for the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$, \mathbf{p}_t^g is updated as follows:

$$\mathbf{p}_{t+1}^g \in \{\mathbf{p}_{t+1}^k, k=1, \dots, m\} \text{ such that } f(\mathbf{p}_{t+1}^g) = \min_{k=1, \dots, m} f(\mathbf{p}_{t+1}^k); \quad (10)$$

r_0, r_1, r_2 are independent random coefficients, uniformly distributed in the range $[0,1]$; c_0, c_1, c_2 are real coefficients called respectively *inertial*, *cognition* and *social parameter*. Normally, the computation is stopped once $t=s$ and the solution is the best individual found so far, *i.e.* \mathbf{p}_s^g , while the minimum so obtained is $f(\mathbf{p}_s^g)$.

The stochastic nature of the algorithm is weighted, in some way, by the presence of the coefficients c_0, c_1, c_2 : the convergence, stability and search domain exploration of the algorithm strongly depend on their value. Unfortunately, the best choice of these parameters is function-dependent, and sometimes it is difficult to find a suitable set of parameters.

In ALE-PSO coefficients $c_j, j=0, 1, 2$ are not fixed, but updated according to a power law ruled by three parameters, $c_{j,0}, c_{j,s}$ and e_j :

$$c_{j,t} = c_{j,s} + (c_{j,0} - c_{j,s}) \left(\frac{s-t}{s-1} \right)^{e_j}, \quad j \in \{0, 1, 2\}, \quad (11)$$

where $c_{j,t}$ is the value of the coefficient c_j at iteration t , $c_{j,s}$ at the end of the iterations ($t=s$) and $c_{j,0}$ at the beginning ($t=0$). The coefficients $c_{j,0}$ and $c_{j,s}$ must be chosen by the user, as well as the power e_j , which modulates the variation of the c_j along the iterations. The strategy for constraint handling in ALE-PSO is essentially a barrier method: the swarm must be feasible at each iteration. For this reason, the initial swarm is composed by feasible particles and then its updates are guaranteed to be feasible by the following procedure (without lack of generality, we consider here constraints of the form $g(\mathbf{x}^k) < 0$):

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k = \mathbf{x}_t^k + \frac{\mathbf{u}_{t+1}^k}{2^\alpha}, \quad \alpha = 0, 1, 2, \dots; \quad \text{stop when } g(\mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k) < 0. \quad (12)$$

As \mathbf{x}_t^k is feasible, this bisection method ensures that, for a sufficiently large α , \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^k will be feasible. In addition, the barrier can be dynamically adapted, *i.e.*, the value of the constraint can be linearly varied through iterations, in order to increase the chance of finding good and feasible points for hard problems.

Let us now consider how to schedule an adaptive variation of coefficients c_0 , c_1 and c_2 . At the beginning of iterations, c_0 and c_1 should have large values and decrease with iterations, the contrary for c_2 ; this should give a good compromise between the exploration and exploitation phases, the first one being more important at an early stage of the computation, the second one at a final stage. Nevertheless, at each iteration c_0 , c_1 and c_2 should respect some conditions of convergence. Two different set of conditions for the convergence of a standard PSO have been considered, those given by Trelea [9] and those given by Jiang *et al* [10]. Trelea used the theory of dynamical systems to obtain the conditions

$$a < 1, \quad b > 0, \quad 2a - b + 2 > 0, \quad \text{with} \quad a = c_0, \quad b = \frac{c_1 + c_2}{2}. \quad (13)$$

Conditions (13) determine a triangular domain in the plane (a, b) ; in addition, Trelea partitioned the triangular domain in five zones having different characteristics of convergence, see Fig. 1: R1, oscillatory convergence; R2, zigzag superposed to an oscillatory convergence; R3, symmetric zigzagging convergence; R4, asymmetric zigzagging convergence; R5, non-oscillatory convergence.

Fig. 1. Trelea's deterministic convergence domain and trajectories of the coefficients

A choice of c_0 , c_1 and c_2 determines a point (a, b) in the region above; if their value changes during iterations, the point (a, b) describes a trajectory in the plane (a, b) .

Jiang *et al*, [10], proposed a different convergence analysis of a PSO standard algorithm, in order to take into account the randomness introduced by coefficients r_0 , r_1 and r_2 . They found the following conditions that can guide the choice of the parameters:

$$0 \leq a < 1, \quad 2b > 0, \quad 0 < \varphi < \varphi_1, \quad \text{where} \\ \varphi = (c_1 + c_2)(1 - c_0^2) + \frac{1}{6}(c_1^2 + c_2^2 + c_1c_2)c_0^2 - \frac{1}{6}(2c_1^2 + 2c_2^2 + 3c_1c_2), \quad \varphi_1 = \frac{1}{6}(1 + c_0)c_2^2. \quad (14)$$

It must be noticed that conditions (14) do not necessarily agree with the Trelea's conditions, because they are derived in a different way.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Several examples have been treated with ALE-PSO, the results concerning three of them are presented below. Some characteristics of the computations have been conserved through all the runs of the code: the population size is constant, $m=100$; the number of generations has been fixed to $s=300$; the original population has been sorted randomly once and for all for all the tests, *i.e.* the tests have been performed on the same starting population for all the cases.

Five different types of calculations have been made, the first two with constant parameters c_0 , c_1 , c_2 , whose values have been suggested by Clerc and Kennedy [11], test T1, and by Trelea [9], test T2. The three others tests have been done with a trajectory of adaptive parameters; the data for the parameters are summarized in Tab. 1. In addition, the trajectories of the tests T3, T4 and T5 are presented in Fig. 1 (tests T1 and T2 reduce to points). All the examples refer to laminates composed by identical T300-5208 carbon-epoxy plies, with a thickness of 0.125 mm and whose characteristics are given in Tab. 2, [12].

Table 1. Numerical data for the tuning of parameters c_0 , c_1 , c_2 in the tests.

Test	$c_{0,0}$	$c_{0,s}$	e_0	$c_{1,0}$	$c_{1,s}$	e_1	$c_{2,0}$	$c_{2,s}$	e_2
T1	0.729	0.729	0	1.490	1.490	0	1.490	1.490	0
T2	0.600	0.600	0	1.700	1.700	0	1.700	1.700	0
T3	1.000	0.500	0.5	5.000	1.500	0.5	1.000	1.800	2
T4	0.800	0.000	0.5	2.000	1.400	0.2	1.400	2.000	0.2
T5	0.400	0.000	0.5	2.000	1.400	0.2	1.400	2.000	0.2

Table 2. Technical, Cartesian and polar constants of carbon-epoxy T300-5208 (GPa).

E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν_{12}	Q_{11}	Q_{22}	Q_{66}	Q_{12}	T_0	T_1	R_0	R_1	Φ_0	Φ_1
181.00	10.30	7.17	0.28	181.81	10.35	7.17	2.89	26.88	24.74	19.71	21.43	0°	0°

The first example concerns a fully isotropic laminates with twelve plies. It is a sort of benchmark in the laminates design field, already treated in the past by the author and co-workers, [13], and by other researchers, [14]. The case of fully isotropy, that comprehends also bending-extension uncoupling, is determined by the choice $H_{ii} = 1$, $i = 3, 4, 9, 10, 15, 16$, the other components being null, so that function $I(\mathbf{P})$ reduces to

$$I(\mathbf{P}) = P_3^2 + P_4^2 + P_9^2 + P_{10}^2 + P_{15}^2 + P_{16}^2 = 0. \quad (15)$$

The results of the numerical tests are summarised in Tab. 3. For each tests, two quantities, obtained in a run for the objective function, are considered: the best value of the average on the swarm and the value of the best particle in the swarm (*i.e.* the particle having the lowest value of the objective function). For both these quantities, the statistics data relative to 100 runs, are: the mean value, the standard deviation, the best value, the worst value and the number of evaluations n_{eval} of the objective function to obtain the quantity's mean value.

The exact solution being 0, the data reported in columns 3, 5 and 6 of Tab. 3 are the numerical residual of the computation. In Fig. 2, it is shown the case of the best particle (test T3), whose stacking sequence is $[-16.43^\circ, -70.38^\circ, 66.70^\circ, 31.97^\circ, 31.76^\circ, -59.02^\circ, 78.65^\circ, -12.13^\circ, -12.34^\circ, -47.06^\circ, -90.00^\circ, 36.06^\circ]$. The directional diagrams of $A_{xx}^* = A_{xx}/h$, $B_{xx}^* = 2 B_{xx}/h^2$ and $D_{xx}^* = 12 D_{xx}/h^3$ are shown; actually, $B_{xx}^* \sim 0$ (almost a dot in the centre of the plot), which confirms that the laminate is uncoupled, while $A_{xx}^* \sim D_{xx}^*$ and they describe a curve very close to a circle of radius $T_0 + 2T_1 = 76.36$ GPa, as it must be for isotropy.

Table 3. Results of the tests T1 to T5 for example 1.

Test	Run's best	Mean value	Standard deviation	Best value	Worst value	n_{eval}
T1	average	0.203	0.194	0.091	0.686	23830
	particle	0.104	0.077	0.023	0.310	29860
T2	average	0.209	0.185	0.024	0.569	27110
	particle	0.114	0.081	0.023	0.310	29980
T3	average	0.211	0.028	0.023	0.860	27030
	particle	0.061	0.022	0.023	0.090	30000
T4	average	0.102	0.072	0.034	0.243	29900
	particle	0.075	0.023	0.034	0.097	29940
T5	average	0.186	0.225	0.024	0.800	29140
	particle	0.126	0.097	0.024	0.383	29980

Fig. 2. Directional diagrams of A_{xx}^* , D_{xx}^* and B_{xx}^* , reduced to a dot (GPa).

Fig. 3. Directional diagrams of A_{xx}^* and D_{xx}^* ($B_{xx}^* \sim 0$) for example 2 (GPa).

Fig. 4. Directional diagrams of A_{xx}^* and D_{xx}^* ($B_{xx}^* \sim 0$) for example 3 (GPa).

The second case is that of a rectangular laminated plate with 12 plies, designed to be uncoupled and orthotropic in bending, with axes of orthotropy at 0° and 90° ; the plate is simply supported, with side lengths along the axes x and y respectively equal to a and b . The additional requirement is that the frequency of the first mode of the bending vibrations must be greater than a minimum specified value ω_0 . So, the objective function is still $I(\mathbf{P})$, but now $H_{ii} = 1$, $i = 9, 10, 17, 18$, so that the problem is defined by

$$I(\mathbf{P}) = P_9^2 + P_{10}^2 + P_{17}^2 + P_{18}^2 = 0, \quad \text{with} \quad g(\mathbf{P}) = \omega_0 - \omega_{pq}(\mathbf{P}) \leq 0 \quad (16)$$

where the frequency $\omega_{pq}(\mathbf{P})$ of the mode having p and q half waves respectively along x and y , is given by, see [15],

$$\omega_{pq}^2 = \frac{\pi^4 p^4 h^3}{12\sigma a^4} \sqrt{R_0^2 + R_1^2} (1 + \chi^2)^2 \varphi(\xi_0, \xi_1), \quad \text{with} \quad (17)$$

$$\varphi(\xi_0, \xi_1) = \tau + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \rho^2}} \left[(-1)^K \rho \xi_0 \frac{\chi^4 - 6\chi^2 + 1}{(1 + \chi^2)^2} + 4\xi_1 \frac{1 - \chi^2}{1 + \chi^2} \right].$$

h is the plate's thickness, σ its mass per unit area and the dimensionless quantities χ , ρ and τ , along with ξ_0 and ξ_1 , the classical bending lamination parameters, are

$$\chi = \frac{qa}{pb}, \quad \rho = \frac{R_0}{R_1}, \quad \tau = \frac{T_0 + 2T_1}{\sqrt{R_0^2 + R_1^2}}, \quad \xi_0 = \frac{1}{np^3} \sum_{j=1}^{np} d_j \cos 4\delta_j, \quad (18)$$

$$\xi_1 = \frac{1}{np^3} \sum_{j=1}^{np} d_j \cos 2\delta_j, \quad d_j = 12j(j - np - 1) + 4 + 3np(np + 2).$$

The results of the numerical tests for this example are shown in Table 4; they refer to the case of a plate with sides $a=1$ m, $b=0.5$ m, designed to have $\omega_{11} \geq \omega_0 = 150$ s⁻¹; the mass of the plate per unit of area is $\sigma=2.4$ kg/m² (12 plies of carbon-epoxy T300-5208). The best result is obtained with the trajectory T3: $[-66.15^\circ, 66.53^\circ, 44.83^\circ, -36.44^\circ, 48.52^\circ, -5.68^\circ, 77.57^\circ, -89.94^\circ, -84.48^\circ, 38.45^\circ, 57.48^\circ, -46.03^\circ]$. For this sequence, $I(\mathbf{P})$ is very close to zero (7.20×10^{-35}) and the frequency $\omega_{11}=162.72$ s⁻¹.

Table 4. Results of the tests T1 to T5 for example 2.

Test	Run's best	Mean value	Standard deviation	Best value	Worst value	n_{eval}
T1	average	9.78×10^{-3}	4.69×10^{-3}	4.50×10^{-3}	1.80×10^{-2}	25510
	particle	1.04×10^{-18}	1.25×10^{-18}	8.00×10^{-21}	3.30×10^{-18}	29800
T2	average	1.37×10^{-2}	8.14×10^{-3}	4.50×10^{-3}	3.20×10^{-2}	26540
	particle	1.47×10^{-18}	3.32×10^{-18}	8.80×10^{-29}	9.90×10^{-18}	29760
T3	average	1.14×10^{-2}	4.58×10^{-2}	4.50×10^{-2}	2.10×10^{-2}	26040
	particle	1.83×10^{-31}	4.74×10^{-31}	7.20×10^{-35}	1.50×10^{-30}	29670
T4	average	1.18×10^{-2}	5.24×10^{-3}	6.60×10^{-3}	2.20×10^{-2}	25840
	particle	3.00×10^{-9}	9.49×10^{-9}	1.30×10^{-34}	3.00×10^{-8}	27800
T5	average	9.33×10^{-3}	3.97×10^{-3}	1.20×10^{-3}	1.30×10^{-2}	24640
	particle	2.24×10^{-18}	6.60×10^{-18}	5.70×10^{-34}	2.10×10^{-17}	27990

Table 5. Example 2: technical, Cartesian and polar constants of the best solution laminate; C_{ij} is a generic Cartesian component (GPa).

	E_x	E_y	G_{xy}	ν_{xy}	C_{xx}	C_{yy}	C_{ss}	C_{xy}	C_{xs}	C_{ys}	T_0	T_1	R_0	R_1	Φ_0	Φ_1
A*	42.3	81.1	29.1	0.2	49.3	96.7	30.1	25.8	3.9	9.9	26.8	24.7	4.4	6.8	-34.4°	74.8°
B*	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	-0.01	0	0	0	0	-	-
D*	27.3	68.3	36.4	0.3	38.2	95.4	36.4	32.1	0	0	26.8	24.7	9.5	7.1	45°	90°

The elastic properties of this laminate are shown in Table 5 and in Fig. 3; they show that the requirements have been satisfied; in addition, the extension behaviour is completely anisotropic, as a result of the fact that no requirement on **A** has been formulated.

The third case is that of an 8-ply laminate orthotropic in bending, uncoupled and with the Young's modulus in the directions x and y constrained to satisfy respectively the conditions $E_x \geq E_1=90$ GPa and $E_y \geq E_2=90$ GPa. In addition, it is required that the orientation angles take values each 5° , *i.e.* 0° , 5° , 10° and so on. The objective function is the same of example 2, but now the constraints to be satisfied are, see [16],

$$E_x = \frac{8[T_0 T_1 + (-1)^K T_1 R_0 \xi_0 - 2R_1^2 \xi_1^2]}{T_0 + 2T_1 + (-1)^K R_0 \xi_0 - 4R_1 \xi_1} \geq E_1, \quad E_y = \frac{8[T_0 T_1 + (-1)^K T_1 R_0 \xi_0 - 2R_1^2 \xi_1^2]}{T_0 + 2T_1 + (-1)^K R_0 \xi_0 + 4R_1 \xi_1} \geq E_2. \quad (19)$$

Table 6. Results of the tests T1 to T5 for example 3.

Test	Run's best	Mean value	Standard deviation	Best value	Worst value	n_{eval}
T1	average	8.30×10^{-3}	2.38×10^{-3}	4.80×10^{-3}	1.30×10^{-2}	25140
	particle	6.25×10^{-4}	9.45×10^{-5}	5.70×10^{-6}	2.40×10^{-4}	9510
T2	average	1.66×10^{-2}	1.25×10^{-2}	1.70×10^{-3}	3.70×10^{-2}	25010
	particle	8.91×10^{-4}	1.35×10^{-3}	2.20×10^{-6}	3.70×10^{-3}	3320
T3	average	8.88×10^{-3}	3.63×10^{-3}	4.30×10^{-3}	1.50×10^{-2}	25480
	particle	7.11×10^{-4}	1.19×10^{-4}	1.00×10^{-6}	3.40×10^{-4}	4910
T4	average	3.59×10^{-3}	5.31×10^{-3}	2.50×10^{-6}	1.80×10^{-2}	22150
	particle	8.32×10^{-4}	8.34×10^{-4}	2.50×10^{-6}	2.50×10^{-3}	5710
T5	average	1.23×10^{-3}	1.88×10^{-3}	1.10×10^{-4}	6.40×10^{-3}	21400
	particle	4.55×10^{-4}	5.65×10^{-4}	8.50×10^{-5}	2.00×10^{-3}	2980

Table 7. Example 3: technical, Cartesian and polar constants of the best solution laminate; C_{ij} is a generic Cartesian component (GPa).

	E_x	E_y	G_{xy}	ν_{xy}	C_{xx}	C_{yy}	C_{ss}	C_{xy}	C_{xs}	C_{ys}	T_0	T_1	R_0	R_1	Φ_0	Φ_1
A*	63.8	77.2	26.3	0.3	69.6	84.3	26.3	22.1	0	0	26.9	24.7	0.6	1.8	0°	90°
B*	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.01	0	0	0.02	0.02	22.5°	45°
D*	112.3	66.2	13.1	0.1	113.5	66.9	13.1	8.8	0	0	26.9	24.7	13.8	5.8	0°	0°

The results of the tests made for this example are shown in Tab. 6. The best result is once again found by trajectory T3, to which corresponds the anti-symmetric sequence $[-5^\circ, -85^\circ, 45^\circ, -55^\circ, 55^\circ, -45^\circ, 85^\circ, 5^\circ]$; for this laminate, the value of the objective function is 10^{-6} , $E_x=112.31$ GPa and $E_y=66.21$ GPa. The elastic properties of this laminate are shown in Table 7 and in Fig. 4; the same remarks made on example 2 can be done again. **A*** and **D*** are $K=0$ orthotropic, for the anti-symmetry of the stack.

5. FINAL REMARKS AND CONCLUSIONS

Some considerations can be done about the results shown above. First of all, they all are some rather exigent problems in laminate design, and ALE-PSO has been able to find numerical solutions that are very close to an exact one. All the examples run for no more than 3.5 seconds on a common laptop. It is interesting to compare the trajectories of the parameters to determine the most performing one. To this purpose it is worth to consider the cases of the expected and best value of the residual, for the swarm average and best particle. The analysis of the data in Tab. 3, 4 and 6 shows that T3 is the most suitable trajectory to find the best value of the solution, in all the cases. For the average of the best value, the three trajectories T3, T4 and T5 are equally performing. For the

expected value, T5 seems to be the best choice. In any case, trajectories T3, T4 or T5 give better results than the cases of T1 and T2, *i.e.* when parameters are fixed.

Concerning the convergence of the computations, the diagrams of convergence of the best particle are shown in Fig. 5 for the three examples above; the diagrams are those of the run containing the best solution found in each case. In the case of example 2, the log-scale diagram is almost linear: the order of magnitude of the residual is linearly decreased along iterations. This seems to be an optimal situation for computations, but unfortunately it is strongly problem-dependent, as diagrams of examples 1 and 3 show. Nevertheless, suitable trajectories of the parameters c_0 , c_1 and c_2 can be found for each problem to push the convergence log-diagrams towards linearity. This should be a guideline for users in the search of a good trajectory for a given problem.

Fig. 5. Convergence diagrams of $J(\mathbf{P})$ for the 3 cases (in small, the curves in log-scale).

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